

Workshop: What does it mean to teach teamwork?

Carola Hernández Hernandez¹, Nicolás Sánchez-Díaz², Carola Gómez³

¹ Profesora Asociada, Unidad de Apoyo a la Docencia, Decanatura, Facultad de Ingeniería, Universidad de los Andes.

² Asistente Graduado de Investigación, Unidad de Apoyo a la Docencia, Decanatura, Facultad de Ingeniería, Universidad de los Andes.

³ Profesora Asistente, Facultad de Educación, Universidad Antonio Nariño.

Email: c-hernan@uniandes.edu.co, sanchezd2@uniandes.edu.co, cagomez14@uan.edu.co

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14062947>

Abstract

Increasingly, transversal competencies take on a more relevant role in engineering education. Working in interdisciplinary teams is one of the great realities of how engineering is developed, and having the skills to do so has become one of the main demands of universities. For this reason, project-oriented courses are increasingly seen in curricular reforms in which students are organized into teams to have an experience closer to their professional performance. However, working in a team is often very difficult, not only for the students but also for the teachers who accompany the teams. In many cases, a strong orientation toward teams achieving the expected products because of the project generates terrible experiences for students who need to develop the skills, attitudes, and knowledge to be part of truly effective teams. Therefore, the purpose of this workshop is to show teachers what implications teaching students to work as a team has for their pedagogical practice, as well as to help them reflect on what type of knowledge they should generate in students so that they can promote the development of these skills. Using experiential learning, participants will form teams of 4 or 5 people in which they will develop a small challenge. This experience will allow the generation of reflective processes that lead participants to recognize the importance of effectively guiding teams and providing students with tools to promote the development of Teamwork competence, emphasizing the skills required. This way, it will be possible to conclude what it means to teach teamwork.

Keywords: Teamwork; Collaborative learning; active learning; socio-emotional skills.

1 Introduction

Teamwork has sparked great interest among employers as an essential skill for solving highly complex problems and coping with the challenges that the 21st century brings to each sector of our society. The benefits of teamwork encompass a wide range of characteristics that allow any institution to advance quickly and effectively in its objectives. For example, working in teams allows for the creation of new and disruptive ideas in the form of co-creation, including different perspectives, experiences, and diversity that contribute to creativity and innovation in the workplace (Tucker & Abbasi, 2012). In general, all productive sectors are highly interested in teamwork to promote workplace synergy, leading to better interaction, development, and achievement of results.

The demand for educating individuals who are increasingly competent in participating in high-performance teams has also generated pressure on educational systems. However, a large number of teachers have the erroneous belief that exposing students to different peer work activities can implicitly develop teamwork. Nevertheless, research in the field has shown that the absence of explicit theorization about teamwork and its characteristics can inevitably lead to an impoverished understanding of the subject, with subsequent unfavorable performance of the competence (Pinard et al., 2017; Therrien et al., 2017). This is in line with the approaches of Marin-Garcia and Lloret (2008), who describe in their study how higher education students consider these types of activities as overwhelming and extremely difficult to manage in the allotted times, even more so when teachers expect good quality in the products developed by the teams.

In light of this scenario, the question arises: What does it mean to teach teamwork? This hands-on workshop emerges from nearly a decade of reflecting on and testing activities in Project-Oriented courses to teach

students how to work in teams (Hernández & Gómez, 2020). These courses, part of the university's basic training cycle (CBU), are offered to all undergraduate students. However, since they originate from the faculty of engineering, about 60% of the students come from various engineering disciplines. Starting from experiential learning and Kolb's cycle, different pedagogical strategies have been identified and put into play in this workshop space.

2 Activities

Teachers will undergo an experience similar to what their students might encounter in a project. The workshop is a simulation of a Kolb cycle (Sharlanova, 2004) concerning teaching teamwork.

In the first moment of the experience's development, we will use the marshmallow challenge. For this, we will work in groups randomly formed among the participants. We will use a marshmallow, a meter of wool, a meter of tape, and twenty spaghetti. The groups will try to build the highest self-sustaining structure with the marshmallow at the top in a maximum of 18 minutes.

In the second moment, they will reflect on their experience with the challenge, the lessons they learned from working in a team, and the needs this generated.

The differences between Teamwork and Group Work are introduced. After this, the skills that come into play when working as a team will be identified, emphasizing those that are oriented towards emotional management and not just oriented to the task or the products. With these elements, the critical elements of Teamwork are recognized.

From this, we reflect on the teacher's role in developing Teamwork competence using the experience lived in the marshmallow challenge and the conceptual components discussed in the third moment of the session.

Finally, with the experience, the theoretical approach, and the reflective discussion, some strategies are proposed to favor the "teaching" Teamwork competence process.

3 Expected results

Three main results are expected: first, participants will experience teamwork through a simple challenge; second, they will reflect on their experience through a guided, collaborative, and negotiated conversation with facilitators and classmates; and third, they will be able to identify the emotional and relational implications of teamwork, besides disciplinary demands of the task. Hence, participants should reflect on their role as teamwork teachers so that they can grasp the elements of emotional management within teams and thus think about strategies for teaching their students to work in teams.

4 References

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